

Metal Complexes with Sulphur Donor Ligands. Part-IV. Some Mixed Xanthate Complexes of Nickel(II) with N-Donor Ligands

T. J. MOHAMMED, IHSAN A. MUSTAFA and S. E. AL-MUKHTAR*

Chemistry Department, College of Science, University of Mosul, Mosul-Iraq

Manuscript received 2 April 1985, accepted 31 July 1985

Some new mixed ligand complexes of nickel(II) having the compositions $Ni(RXan)_2$, $Ni(RXan)_2L_2$ and $Ni(RXan)_2L'$, where $RXan = 2$ -methoxyethylxanthate and 2-ethoxyethyl xanthate; $L =$ pyridine, β -picoline, γ -picoline, 3,5-lutidine, 3,5-dichloropyridine or isoquinoline; and $L' = 1,10$ -phenanthroline, 2,2'-iminodipyridine or 2,2'-dipyridyl have been synthesised and characterised on the basis of elemental analysis, magnetic susceptibility, infrared and electronic spectral studies. The free base complexes are diamagnetic, while the base adducts and the tris(xanthato) complexes are paramagnetic with distorted octahedral structures. Relevant ligand field parameters have been calculated for the six-coordinated complexes.

It is well established that sulphur is a potential donor for the transition metals¹. In comparison to other sulphur containing ligands, reaction of xanthates with transition metals have not been systematically studied. Reported works^{2,3} on this subject indicate that interaction of xanthate complexes of nickel(II) with various nitrogenous bases are related closely to the electronic properties of the ligands. In continuation to our previous work⁴⁻⁶ on the preparation of mixed ligand complexes with sulphur donor ligands, we have now prepared some complexes of nickel(II) containing xanthates and various nitrogenous bases. The xanthates are 2-methoxyethylxanthate (MeXan) and 2-ethoxyethylxanthate (EtXan).

Experimental

Potassium xanthates were prepared from their corresponding alcohols by literature method⁷.

$Ni(RXan)_2$: Aqueous solution of nickel(II) chloride was added to an aqueous solution of xanthate in 1 : 2 molar ratio. The resulting brown precipitates were filtered, washed with water and dried under vacuum

$Ni(RXan)_2L_2$ ($L = py, \beta$ -pic, γ -pic, 3,5-lut, 3,5-pyCl₂ or isoquin): 60% ethanolic solution of hydrated nickel(II) chloride was added slowly with stirring to 60% ethanolic solution of KRXan. To the brown suspension formed, an excess of the nitrogenous base in ethanol was added with stirring. The resulting green, grass-green or pale green pastes, were then dissolved in acetone and filtered. Upon slow evaporation of the solvent, crystals of the corresponding complexes deposited, which were collected and dried under vacuum.

$Ni(RXan)_2L'$, ($L' = 1,10$ -phen, 2,2'-iminodipy or 2,2'-dipy): Addition of an excess of L' in ether (ethanol in the case of 1,10-phen) to brown solution of the metal xanthate mixture in ether (ethanol in case of 1,10-phen), gave olive-green (bluish green for 2,2'-iminodipy) precipitates. The precipitates were filtered off, washed several times with either (in case of 1,10-phen washed with 1,10-phen in ethanol and then with ethanol) and dried under vacuum.

$[R'_4N]Ni(RXan)_2$, ($R' = CH_3, C_2H_5$): An excess of tetraalkyl ammonium chloride solution was added with stirring to an aqueous solution of KRXan. To it an aqueous solution of nickel(II) chloride was added slowly with stirring in 3 : 1 molar ratio. The resulting green precipitates were filtered off, dried and recrystallised from acetone to give green crystals.

C, H, N and S analyses were carried out in Micro-Analytical Laboratories, Alfred Bernhardt, W. Germany. Nickel was determined gravimetrically as nickel dimethylglyoxime.

Infrared spectra were scanned on a Perkin-Elmer 557 spectrophotometer (200-4 000 cm⁻¹). Reflectance spectra were recorded on a Unicam SP700C spectrophotometer. Magnetic measurements were made at room temperature by the Gouy method on the solids. Both reflectance spectra and magnetic measurements were carried out at the Chemistry Department, University of Surrey, U.K.

Results and Discussion

The analytical results are in agreement with general formulae of the nickel complexes (Table 1). Nitrogenous bases, such as pyridine and substituted

pyridine form 2 : 1 base adducts with the base-free complexes $Ni(RXan)_2$, whereas 1,10-phen, 2,2'-iminodipy and 2,2'-dipy form 1 : 1 base adducts with the base-free complexes. The green compound obtained from the reaction of 3,5-dichloropyridine with $Ni(MeXan)_2$, decomposed after a few minutes. Reaction of other nitrogenous bases, such as quinoline and 2,6-picoline with the base-free complexes results in the formation of viscous solution, and thus the complexes could not be crystallised. Our attempts to isolate adducts with oxygen donor ligands, such as THF, DMSO and pyridine oxide, failed, and no indication of their formation could be detected. Ligand field effect produced by N-bases stabilises nickel(II) complexes relative to O-donor ligands⁸.

Infrared spectra : Infrared spectra of the base adducts were compared with those of the base free complexes. In agreement with earlier assignments^{9,10}, the strong band at 1 260 and 1 265 cm^{-1} in the spectra of the two base-free nickel complexes can be assigned to asymmetric C—O stretching

tion, these bands shifted to lower frequencies (1 180–1 200 cm^{-1}) suggesting that the canonical

in the base adducts and tris(xanthato) complexes as compared to the base-free complexes. The additional ligand donates electron density to the metal ion and the complex becomes more ionic in character, which results in decreasing the C—O bond order and its absorption is shifted to lower frequency. The band observed at 1 048 cm^{-1} in the spectra of the base-free complexes, which is assigned^{9,11} to C—S stretching frequency, shifted to higher frequencies (1 055–1 068 cm^{-1}) in the base adducts and tris(xanthato) complexes of the two ligands. This shift indicates an increase in the π -character of the C—S bond on adduct formation. Similar increase in C—S frequency for nickel(II) xanthate have been reported⁸. The strong, sharp bands observed at 380 and 383 cm^{-1} in the spectra of the two base-free complexes were assigned to Ni—S stretching frequency^{9,12}. These bands were absent in the spectra of the free ligands. On adduct formation, Ni—S bands shifted to lower frequencies (365–375 cm^{-1}). Apparently, the nickel ion demand for sulphur electrons in the base-free complexes decreases on adduct formation, thus lowering the Ni—S bond order and shifting its absorption to lower frequency.

The changes observed in the ν_{C-O} , ν_{C-S} and ν_{Ni-S} modes on going from base-free to base adduct

complexes, confirm^{13,14} bonding of the nitrogenous ligands, L or L', to the nickel ion.

Magnetic properties : The diamagnetic nature of the base-free complexes (Table 1), suggests their low-spin square planar geometry. All the base adducts and the tris(xanthato) complexes are paramagnetic. The magnetic moment values for these adducts (2.93–3.30 B.M.) are typical¹⁵ of high-spin octahedral complexes of nickel(II).

Electronic spectra : The bands observed in the diffuse reflectance spectra and their assignments are given in Table 1. The diamagnetic base-free complexes show two ligand field bands, one at 15 267, 17 241 cm^{-1} attributed to $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1A_{2g}$ transition and the other at 20 618, 21 505 cm^{-1} attributed to $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1B_{1g}$ transition for $Ni(Et-RXan)_2$ and $Ni(MeRXan)_2$, respectively. The position of these bands and the absence of any other absorption below 10 000 cm^{-1} confirm the square planar geometry assigned for the two bis-(xanthato) nickel(II) complexes. The electronic spectra of the base adducts show two strong bands. The first spin-allowed band $^3A_{2g} \rightarrow ^3T_{2g}$ (F) is centered at 10 000 cm^{-1} , and is split by $\sim 1\ 000\ cm^{-1}$. The split of the low energy transition, indicates^{16,17} a deviation from O_h symmetry which may be due to tetragonal distortion, since under tetragonal symmetry (D_{4h}), the $^3T_{2g}$ state splits into $^3B_{2g}$ and 3E_g states. The second spin-allowed band $^3A_{2g} \rightarrow ^3T_{1d}$ (F) is centered at $\sim 16\ 000\ cm^{-1}$ and shows some asymmetry on the high frequency side in the spectra of some of the base adducts. The third ligand field band $^3A_{2g} \rightarrow ^3T_{1g}$ (P), which is expected to occur at $\sim 25\ 000\ cm^{-1}$ (Table 1) is not observed probably because being masked by the tall end of the strong charge transfer band. A weak band, usually occurring as a shoulder to the nearby charge transfer band is seen in some adducts at 21 000–21 700 cm^{-1} which may be due to spin-forbidden $^3A_{2g} \rightarrow ^1T_{2g}$ (D) transition. The ν_3 band position of the base adducts has been calculated from their ν_1 and ν_2 band positions, the calculated value of ν_3 position being within the range 24 379–26 928 cm^{-1} . The spectra of the tris(xanthato) complexes are similar to that of the nitrogen base adducts except in that the absorption bands are shifted to lower frequencies, which is in accord with the weak field nature of the sulphur containing ligand. The observed spin-allowed transition has been utilised to obtain ligand field parameters. The ν_3/ν_1 values (ca. 1.52–1.62) support^{18,19} the octahedral geometry assigned to these complexes and suggest²⁰ a strong configuration interaction between the high spin T_{1g} (P) and T_{2g} (F) excited states. Calculated values of Racah parameters (B) lie in the range 621–844 cm^{-1} in these complexes. The results are in good agreement with those reported^{21,22} for octahedral nickel(II) complexes.

The calculated values of β (0.580–0.782) indicate a moderate degree of covalent character among the

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL, ANALYTICAL AND MAGNETIC DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Compd.	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			Diamag.	μ_{eff} B.M.	$\nu_1(\text{cm}^{-1})$ $\nu_2(\text{cm}^{-1})$	$\nu_3^*(\text{cm}^{-1})$ $\nu_4^*(\text{cm}^{-1})$	ν_5 ν_6	β^{**}	LFSE kcal mol ⁻¹	E _p (cm ⁻¹) Term sep.
		C	H	Ni								
Ni(EtR ₂ Xan) ₂	Brown	30.64 (30.85)	4.58 (4.66)	—	15.24 (15.08)	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Ni(MeR ₂ Xan) ₂	Brown	26.45 (26.60)	3.87 (3.90)	—	15.96 (16.25)	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Ni(EtR ₂ Xan) ₂ (py) ₂	Grass- green	43.45 (43.88)	5.05 (5.11)	5.09 (5.11)	10.70 (10.72)	10 101	15 873	25 368	1.57	0.675	34.68	10 938
Ni(EtR ₂ Xan) ₂ (β-pic) ₂	Grass- green	45.65 (45.91)	5.63 (5.60)	4.88 (4.86)	10.23 (10.20)	10 204	16 326	26 427	1.60	0.749	35.03	12 141
Ni(EtR ₂ Xan) ₂ (γ-pic) ₂	Grass- green	45.73 (45.91)	5.65 (5.60)	4.87 (4.86)	10.11 (10.20)	10 362	16 129	24 983	1.56	0.631	35.57	10 230
Ni(EtR ₂ Xan) ₂ (3,5-pyCl ₂) ₂	Green	35.04 (35.05)	3.54 (3.53)	4.05 (4.08)	8.72 (8.56)	10 752	16 393	25 442	1.52	0.591	36.91	9 579
Ni(EtR ₂ Xan) ₂ (3,5-lut) ₂	Green	47.60 (47.76)	6.08 (6.01)	4.57 (4.64)	9.73 (9.72)	10 309	15 686	24 558	1.52	0.580	35.39	9 316
Ni(EtR ₂ Xan) ₂ (isoquin) ₂	Green	51.68 (51.93)	5.02 (4.98)	4.24 (4.32)	9.20 (9.06)	10 204	15 873	25 170	1.56	0.644	35.03	10 431
Ni(EtR ₂ Xan) ₂ (1,10-phen)	Olive green	45.67 (46.40)	4.45 (4.60)	4.76 (4.91)	10.25 (10.31)	10 309	16 460	26 928	1.60	0.769	35.39	12 460
Ni(EtR ₂ Xan) ₂ (2,2'-dipy)	Olive green	44.17 (44.04)	4.68 (4.80)	4.97 (5.13)	10.55 (10.76)	10 309	16 393	26 551	1.59	0.739	35.39	11 971
Ni(EtR ₂ Xan) ₂ (2,2'-iminodipy)	Bluish green	42.97 (42.86)	4.76 (4.85)	7.80 (7.49)	10.25 (10.47)	10 416	16 000	25 120	1.54	0.610	35.76	9 882
[Et ₂ N]Ni(EtR ₂ Xan) ₂	Green	40.26 (40.34)	6.98 (6.91)	2.02 (2.04)	8.32 (8.57)	9 345	14 925	24 371	1.60	0.695	32.08	11 260
[Me ₂ N]Ni(EtR ₂ Xan) ₂	Green	36.45 (36.30)	6.41 (6.25)	2.29 (2.22)	9.12 (9.33)	9 389	14 880	23 904	1.58	0.655	32.23	10 617
Ni(MeR ₂ Xan) ₂ (py) ₂	Green	41.13 (41.62)	4.55 (4.65)	5.14 (5.39)	11.13 (11.30)	10 000	16 129	26 534	1.61	0.782	34.33	12 663
Ni(MeR ₂ Xan) ₂ (β-pic) ₂	Green	43.89 (43.88)	5.17 (5.15)	4.97 (5.11)	10.45 (10.72)	9 900	15 625	24 859	1.58	0.666	33.99	10 784
Ni(MeR ₂ Xan) ₂ (γ-pic) ₂	Green	43.72 (43.88)	5.13 (5.15)	5.05 (5.11)	10.51 (10.72)	10 309	15 948	25 019	1.55	0.617	35.39	9 995
Ni(MeR ₂ Xan) ₂ (3,5-lut) ₂	Pale green	45.62 (45.91)	5.40 (5.60)	4.62 (4.86)	10.05 (10.20)	10 204	15 625	24 379	1.53	0.580	35.03	9 392
Ni(MeR ₂ Xan) ₂ (isoquin) ₂	Pale green	50.49 (50.41)	4.41 (4.55)	4.46 (4.52)	9.25 (9.47)	10 256	16 260	26 027	1.59	0.711	35.21	11 519
Ni(MeR ₂ Xan) ₂ (1,10-phen)	Olive green	44.27 (44.37)	4.06 (4.09)	5.39 (5.17)	10.62 (10.84)	10 309	16 528	26 860	1.60	0.769	35.39	12 461
Ni(MeR ₂ Xan) ₂ (2,2'-dipy)	Olive green	41.60 (41.78)	4.01 (4.28)	5.24 (5.41)	11.12 (11.34)	10 309	16 339	26 152	1.58	0.711	35.39	11 519
Ni(MeR ₂ Xan) ₂ (2,2'-iminodipy)	Bluish green	40.36 (40.61)	4.21 (4.35)	7.80 (7.89)	10.95 (11.02)	10 000	16 000	26 000	1.60	0.740	34.33	12 000
[Et ₂ N]Ni(MeR ₂ Xan) ₂	Green	37.24 (37.38)	6.37 (6.43)	2.14 (2.17)	8.92 (9.13)	9 259	15 037	24 533	1.62	0.728	31.79	11 793
[Me ₂ N]Ni(MeR ₂ Xan) ₂	Green	32.80 (32.76)	5.57 (5.67)	2.33 (2.38)	9.86 (10.00)	9 433	14 925	23 994	1.58	0.655	32.39	10 620

*Calculated (*K. F. Purcell and J. C. Kotz, "Inorganic Chemistry", W. B. Saunders Company, 1977, p. 572).

**β = $\frac{B}{B_0} - \frac{B}{1080}$ (where, B = Racah parameter value in the free ion state).

hexacoordinated complexes. The LFSE comes out to be $\sim 35 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$ for the base adducts and $\sim 32 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$ for the tris(xanthato) complexes. The term separation, $E(^4P) - E(^4F)$, of $\sim 11\,000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ corresponds to about 60-80% of the free ion value.

References

1. S. E. LIVINGSTONE, *Quart. Rev. (London)*, 1965, 19, 386.
2. D. COUCOUVANIS and J. P. FACKLER, JR., *Inorg. Chem.*, 1967, 6, 2047.
3. A. G. KRUGER and G. WINTER, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1971, 24, 161.
4. A. F. KAZZER, I. A. MUSTAFA and S. E. AL-MUKHTAR, *J. Educat. Sci. (Iraq)*, 1981, 3, 91.
5. I. A. MUSTAFA and S. E. AL-MUKHTAR, *Raf. J. Sci. (Iraq)*, 1981, 4, 13.
6. E. M. AL-RUFAIE, I. A. MUSTAFA and S. E. AL-MUKHTAR, *Iraq. J. Sci.*, 1984, communicated.
7. I. S. SHUPE, *J. Assoc. Off. Agric. Chemists*, 1942, 25, 495 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1942, 36, 4670).
8. L. E. ORGEL, "An Introduction to Transition Metal Chemistry", Methuen, London, 1960.
9. G. W. WATT and B. J. McCORMICK, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1965, 21, 753.
10. U. AGARWALA, LAKSHMI and P. B. RAO, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1968, 2, 337.
11. T. J. HURLEY and M. A. ROBINSON, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, 7, 33.
12. A. RAY, D. N. SATHYANARAYANA, G. D. PRASAD and C. C. PATEL, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 1973, 29, 1579.
13. G. B. DEACON and R. J. PHILLIPS, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1978, 31, 1709.
14. N. W. ALCOCK, V. M. TRACY and T. C. WADDINTON, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1976, 2243.
15. B. N. FIGGIS and J. LEWIS, "Modern Coordination Chemistry", Interscience, New York, 1960, p. 400.
16. C. R. HARE and C. J. BALLHAUSEN, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1964, 40, 788.
17. D. R. MARKS, D. J. PHILLIPS and J. P. REDFERN, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1967, 1464.
18. M. R. ROSENTHAL and R. S. DRAGO, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, 4, 840.
19. J. MICHAEL and P. A. WALTON, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1975, 37, 71.
20. A. B. P. LEVER, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1968, 3, 119.
21. K. C. PATEL and D. E. GOLDBERG, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1972, 34, 637.
22. M. P. TEOTIA, D. K. RASTOGI and W. U. MALIK, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1973, 7, 343.